

In-band Collection and Control of End-to-end Latency in Programmable Packet-Optical Networks

Faris Alhamed^{1,*}, Andrea Sgambelluri¹,
Chrysa Papagianni², and Francesco Paolucci^{3,*}

¹ Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa, Italy;

² University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam, The Netherlands; ³ CNIT, Pisa, Italy

*faris.alhamed@santannapisa.it, francesco.paolucci@cnit.it

Abstract: A novel programmable INT collector, acting as active controller within the data plane, is proposed to enable fast closed-loop flow latency monitoring. Experimental evaluation on P4-based hardware switches demonstrates assurance reactions within few microseconds. © 2025 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

As network technologies evolve, operators rely on comprehensive network intelligence for full-scale automation, essential for managing complexity and meeting Quality of Service (QoS) and Service Level Agreement (SLA) requirements. Network telemetry plays a key role by providing deep monitoring and enabling automated network management [1]. With the rise of programmable data planes in hybrid packet-optical networks, in-band network telemetry (INT) has emerged as a promising solution, offering notable benefits such as real-time and detailed visibility into network activity. This is achieved by embedding network state metadata directly into packet headers, allowing to handle in-network measurements without involving the control plane. Recent releases of P4-enabled collectors exploit joint per-node and end-to-end metadata statistics extraction that can be consumed by external AI-based agents, thus enabling near real-time service assurance [2, 3].

However, the rapid collection of metadata statistics is necessary, but not sufficient to trigger a fast, real-time local-loop network intervention in the case of SLA violation. In the context of latency-sensitive services, end-to-end latency exceeding a certain threshold due to network congestion may be detrimental and difficult to manage. In addition, considering emerging services such as distributed/federated learning, when highly bursty traffic is experienced, frequent short-time congestions may occur, thus implying, besides latency violations, packet loss and retransmissions, ultimately leading to significant service disruptions and delays [4]. Such micro congestions, with a duration in the order of tens of microseconds, cannot be recovered relying on network agents at the control/management plane, due to the time needed to process telemetry data at higher layers. In fact, near real-time reoptimizations have been demonstrated to be effective in the tens-hundreds milliseconds duration timescale [5].

Driven by the need for faster feedback loops, we introduce a novel approach focused on in-network control of traffic flows using extended INT and a novel Data Plane Active Collector (DPAC). Our solution enhances network responsiveness by enabling both collection of distributed metadata and decision-making directly within the data plane. Specifically, we demonstrate dynamic and adaptable traffic steering coordinated by the DPAC, achieved by: (i) rapidly detecting changes in network conditions, such as early signs of congestion, and (ii) utilizing novel in-band communication channels to exchange control messages. This allows the network to instantly reroute traffic via alternative paths that maintain QoS, all without control/management plane intervention. The proposed approach aims to significantly reduce monitoring reaction times to guarantee the desired flow latency.

2. In-band Network Telemetry Scenario for Latency-sensitive Services

The scenario employing INT and the proposed DPAC is shown in Fig. 1. A packet-optical metro network is considered, in which nodes N1-N6 exploit P4 pipeline programmability and are connected with optical pluggables or using dedicated optical bypass connectivity through a ROADM (e.g., nodes N1 and N6). The network is handled by a Software Defined Network (SDN) Controller with programmable data plane features (e.g., employing the P4Runtime API). Flows f_1 and f_2 are configured following N1-N3-N5-N6 and N2-N3-N5-N6 routes, respectively. Moreover, INT is configured along the flows to collect hop latency metadata. For example, concerning f_1 , N1 is configured as INT source node, N3 and N5 as transit, and N6 as sink node. INT Reports (Rpt) are forwarded by the sink node to the two-stage INT Collector, partially implemented in the data plane space, storing hop latency statistics in dedicated registers, both in a per-node and a per-flow fashion [2]. Then, in the standard INT approach,

Fig. 1. Closed-loop latency assurance steps and delays: standard INT (a), proposed DPAC (b).

shown in Fig. 1(a), statistics averaged over a time window are exported to dedicated Control Agents, in charge of checking SLA violations. Finally, the violation feedback is sent to the controller for service assurance intervention at the source node (e.g., flow rule to enforce priority change or traffic steering).

The whole process of acquiring, aggregating, exporting and analyzing latency metadata towards a control agent, typically deployed as a docker container or a Kubernetes pod in the control plane space, is prone to additional closed-loop execution delay. In fact, typical delay values in the data plane (e.g., based on programmable hardware ASIC) are in the order of few microseconds, while control plane processing and message propagation (i.e., running on general purpose CPU-based backends) are in the order of tens (or hundreds) of millisecond. If, as shown in Fig. 1(a), congestions of duration of some milliseconds occur due to concurrent queuing in the same transit node (e.g., at node N3 forwarding both f_1 and f_2 out of the same link), the closed-loop may take an amount of time greater than the congestion event duration. Hence, the controller adapts its forwarding policies to an out-of-dated event. In addition, latency violation and packet loss has already occurred during the congestion before the controller could take a decision. Finally, the computed actions become useless and potentially dangerous, producing unstable forwarding flaps without any advantage on end-to-end latency SLA assurance.

3. Data Plane Active Collector: proposed INT messages and implementation

To reduce the closed-loop delay, while enabling the network to react quickly to micro congestions, we introduce a new telemetry and routing scheme. The concept works by assigning labels to the packets crossing the INT domain. Such labels have a global significance over the managed domain and serve in identifying routes and flows. We also introduce the Data Plane Active Collector (DPAC), shown in Fig. 1(b). This advanced collector, besides receiving INT Reports and storing latency statistics, implements the logic of checking end-to-end SLA violation for a given amount of packets belonging to a flow or a set of flows. Then, it sends a novel INT control message, called In-Network Control (INC), to perform specific forwarding/priority actions in one or more involved nodes of the considered flow. All the closed-loop steps are fully embedded in the data plane space. In our implementation, the INC message is sent to the ingress node of the identified path to enforce the desired match/action rule on the considered flow. For example, in the case of f_2 congestion at node N3, the INC message is generated towards the INT source node (i.e., N2) to steer some of the traffic -identified by its label- on a backup path, e.g., the N1-N6 optical bypass or the N2-N4-N6 alternative route. The INC extra header fields, all 2-bytes encoded, are the target *node-id*, the *label* identifying the flow and the *backup-port* indication where to steer the flow. As shown in Fig. 1(b), the closed-loop reaction time includes the INT processing (flowchart shown in Fig. 2), the INT Reports, the processing at the DPAC and the backward INC message forwarding. The DPAC flowchart is shown in Fig. 3 and includes the latency violation check computed from the Report, the backup port assignment and the INC message creation. Considering that the DPAC is entirely programmed in the data plane, the closed-loop delay is expected to be reduced, mainly depending on the INT congestion contribution. Thus, recovery takes place when congestion is still occurring, impacting on burst of few milliseconds duration. Anyway, the DPAC benefits impacts longer congestions as well, reducing the recovery time and SLA violation duration.

Fig. 2. Processing flowchart of nodes along the path.

Fig. 3. DPAC processing flowchart.

Fig. 4. DPAC Resource usage.

Fig. 5. Closed-loop delay (μ s).

Fig. 6. INT Overhead.

4. Experimental Results

The DPAC solution has been evaluated experimentally on a packet-optical network testbed, composed of 5 P4 switches running the P4 NIKSS software switch [6], based on the eBPF backend technology, and a pair of Ericsson SPO PM-QPSK coherent cards at 100Gb/s, acting as optical bypass link (see Fig. 1). The DPAC collector P4 code is compiled and deployed into a commercially available Tofino P4 switch (programmable ASIC with 6.5Tb/s backplane throughput) equipped with 100Gb/s optical Ethernet interfaces. To compare DPAC results, a control plane distributed agent [5] and a custom SDN/P4 controller [3] have been included in the testbed.

Fig. 4 shows the resources occupancy of the DPAC pipelines deployed in the ASIC, with focus on the increase in memory (SRAM) as a percentage compared to a simple IP forwarding application and amounts to around 10% per extra configured backup path, this extra memory is used for deploying tables and stateful objects. Also, it shows the increase in Packet Header Vector (PHV) resource usage which varies from around 2% for a single backup path to 3% for three backup paths. In the Tofino architecture, a PHV is the data structure storing packet header fields and metadata, enabling packet processing and decision-making (e.g., forwarding, dropping, modifying) as each packet moves through the P4 pipeline.

Fig. 5 shows the closed-loop delays measured in the testbed using the DPAC, compared with the standard scenario employing the INT collector, the Control Agent and the SDN controller. Results show a reaction time to SLA violations in the order of tens of microseconds, compared to a measured reaction time by the software controller in the order of tens of milliseconds.

Finally, to measure the scalability of the system as a function of the route length, Fig. 6 reports the overhead in terms of total increase in bytes and as a percentage, assuming a packet length of 1500 bytes, this increase is linear, as the number of bytes inserted at each node along the path is the same, except for the ingress node which adds in addition to its latency data, a label and saves the ether-type field of the Ethernet header.

5. Conclusion

We proposed an approach to enhance end-to-end latency control using extended INT and a Data Plane Active Collector (DPAC). By enabling distributed metadata collection and localized decision-making in the data plane, the solution provides significantly faster feedback, detects congestion early, and dynamically reroutes traffic to maintain QoS without relying on slower control planes. Results on the P4 Tofino switch platform show closed loop delays of tens of microseconds, improving service assurance for latency-sensitive and high-burst traffic.

Acknowledgment. The research leading to these results has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under G.A. No. 101096466 (DESIRE6G). Special thanks to Gergely Pongracz (Ericsson Hungary) for his insightful support.

References

1. “Network Telemetry Framework,” RFC 9232 (2022).
2. F. Alhamed, D. Scano, P. Castoldi, J. J. V. Olmos, I. Vershkov, F. Paolucci, and F. Cugini, “P4 telemetry collector,” *Comput. Networks* **227**, 109727 (2023).
3. P. González *et al.*, “Distributed multi-agent system fed with telemetry data for near-real-time service operation,” in *2024 Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, (2024), pp. 1–3.
4. J. Zerwas, K. Aykurt, S. Schmid, and A. Blenk, “Network traffic characteristics of machine learning frameworks under the microscope,” in *17th International Conference on Network and Service Management (CNSM)*, (2021), pp. 207–215.
5. S. Barzegar *et al.*, “Near real-time autonomous multi-flow routing with dynamic optical bypass management,” in *2024 International Conference on Optical Network Design and Modeling (ONDM)*, (2024), pp. 1–3.
6. T. Osiński, J. Palimaka, M. Kossakowski, F. D. Tran, E.-F. Bonfoh, and H. Tarasiuk, “A novel programmable software datapath for software-defined networking,” (2022), *CoNEXT ’22*, p. 245–260.